

A FRAMEWORK FOR THE AUTOMATED DATA-DRIVEN CONSTITUTIVE CHARACTERIZATION OF COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY

We present advances on the development of a mechatronically and algorithmically automated framework for the data-driven identification of constitutive material models based on energy density considerations. These models can capture both the linear and nonlinear constitutive response of multiaxially loaded composite materials in a manner that accounts for progressive damage.

Keywords: Energy density, Data-Driven, Framework, Constitutive behaviour, Material characterization, Inverse methods, Multi-axial loading, Progressive damage

INTRODUCTION

The need to predict the deformation behaviour of continuous systems under complex generalized loading conditions is primarily driven from the need to design and utilize such systems in various areas of human technological endeavours. The means of addressing this need through the ages has been mostly encapsulated by the application of hypotheticodeductive scientific method within the context of continuum mechanics. Successful models have been traditionally considered to be those that can faithfully and accurately reproduce actual (usually experimentally established) behaviour of existing systems. This corresponds to the validation stage of the hypotheticodeductive methodology.

The contemporary demands for cost and time reduction, multi-mission design requirements, and increased systemic complexity resulting from the need for realistic systems predictive simulation (usually resulting in very computation intensive mathematical models), constitute the technology-push motivators for automation of research. On the other hand, the innate human tendency for satisfying curiosity and for engineering elegance and efficient solutions that solve problems both on a societal

or/and a personal scale, along with the rampant yet predictable evolution of computational and other associated technologies are the primary science pull motivators for attempting to automate the research process in general and its application to composites in particular.

In responding to this needs and opportunities our framework follows the industrial-inductive scientific method in order to take advantage of its intrinsic validation characteristics. This is achieved with the help of the analytical model representing the constitutive behaviour of the material is built by an inverse methodology based on systematically acquired experimental data that express energy balance considerations.

Specifically, as shown in Fig. 1, the general procedure of our framework involves the determination of a system model based on the generalized design optimization idea of minimizing the error between the measured behaviours of the actual system and the system model under construction. This occurs while an experimental frame controls the input excitation of both the physical system and its model and at the same time it measures the inputs and the outputs.

Figure 1. Process of identifying the model of a physical system via an experimental frame.

While the optimizer section of the diagram is responsible for adjusting the form of system model so its outputs match the physical system outputs, the controller section is responsible for adjusting aspects of the experimental setup behaviour under the same conditions and under a frozen representation of the system model. In this context determination of the system model is the activity of a system identification that for the case of a continuum structural system amounts to the structural behaviour identification and eventually the characterization of the constitutive response of the material system involved. Since this activity is data-driven (based on the behaviour data of the systemic response acquired by the experimental frame) and leads into the model determination, it belongs to a special category of inverse problems.

In the subsequent sections of this paper an overview of the experimental procedure is described followed by the computational approach and the conclusions.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The industrialized-deductive scientific method in order to achieve high reliability behavioural prediction [1- 3], requires acquiring massive amounts of facts in the form of

experimental data. This suggests that a capability to amplify the natural human ability to perform experiments is necessary. In this spirit, mechanical, hydraulic, electric, and computational power (in the form of robotic systems) have been combined to amplify not only the human ability for deforming material specimens, but also the ability to gather and process sensor data in real time. The degree of automation employed in material testing through the combination of computational and testing machine technologies has evolved extensively in the last 40 years. Mechatronic testing machines were developed to achieve industrial rates of acquisition of observations about material behaviour. More detailed expositions of the evolution of systems used for material constitutive behaviour identification with less or equal to 3 degrees of Freedom (DoF) are given elsewhere [1-3]. Here we will only present the evolution of our efforts as they relate to the most recent of the 6-DoF systems developed at NRL because of its relevance to our current activities.

6-DoF Robotic Systems for Material Characterization

In order to address issues of large specimens, with combined in and out of plane loading a series of 6-DoF testing machines was developed at NRL. A short history of their evolution is given elsewhere [4, 5].

The last two variations of 6-DoF test machines referred to as NRL66.2 and NRL 66.3 were built in a hexapod configuration that was originally developed for flight simulator platforms (Stewart platform) and it is classifiable as a 6-6p parallel robotic mechanism. The hexapod architecture made the machine more compact, far stiffer (less prone to energy storage by deformation of the machine itself). The movable grip is attached to the upper movable 3-armed star-shaped base of the system. The construction phase of the current version of this system (NRL66.3) is nearing completion as shown in Fig. 2. It features an automated specimen feeding device, a wireless sensor network infrastructure, and for the first time it will employ a whole-field 3D optical method for measuring the displacement and strain fields on the surface of the specimen.

(a)

(b)

Figure 2. 3D geometry model of complete NRL66.3 (a) and recent view of system under construction (b)

The role of NRL66.3 is to serve as a data-generator for identifying the material response. It has been designed to control the rigid body motion of the boundary of the specimen that is held by the movable grip and at the same time measure the boundary displacements and tractions at the grips, and the whole field displacement distributions along with the derivable strain fields. The 6-6p architecture of the actuators of the NRL66.3 allows it to move in a manner that the resulting motion involves 6 DoFs relative to any frame of reference. The motivation for this 6-dimensional excitation is based on the anticipation that all possible combinations of loading are expected to generate the widest possible variations of the strain tensor components and thus will excite the constitutive system in a manner that will force the model under construction to be aware of them. This will allow the recovered constitutive model to be able to reproduce them consistently.

Specimen Geometry

The typical flat specimen geometry is shown in Fig. 3 where the dark gray areas indicate the part of the specimen that is placed into the grips, and the light gray area is the area that deforms under the influence of the applied loading. The double notches on the specimen are introduced to disturb the strain field and to ensure that some areas of the specimen (not necessarily near the notch roots) will experience non-linear constitutive response due to the corresponding strain fields. Any geometrical feature that could have this effect would be acceptable in our formulation. However, the notches are very economic and practical from a specimen manufacturing perspective and this was the main reason motivating this selection.

Figure 3. Typical geometry of NRL66.3 specimen

Assuming that the lower grip stays fixed during the experiments, the upper grip has the capability to apply 6-DoF motion that is equivalent to applying three translations t_x, t_y, t_z and three rotations r_x, r_y, r_z . An arbitrary grip motion can always be resolved into these six basis components. Considering these as the loading excitation components, then the corresponding response of the system can be described in terms of the reaction forces f_x, f_y, f_z and moments m_x, m_y, m_z . Therefore, the measuring system of the NRL66.3 is designed to acquire all 6+6=12 measurements corresponding to both groups of these quantities (i.e. 6 controlled kinematic inputs defining the pose of the movable grip and thus the motion of the specimen, and the corresponding 6 reaction quantities).

For the sake of dimensional homogeneity we introduce the two column arrays

$$\mathbf{u} = (u_1, u_2, u_3, u_4, u_5, u_6)^T = (t_x \cdot t_y, t_z, r_x \cdot l_c, r_y \cdot l_c, r_z \cdot l_c)^T \quad (1)$$

$$\mathbf{f} = (f_1, f_2, f_3, f_4, f_5, f_6)^T = (f_x, f_y, f_z, m_x / l_c, m_y / l_c, m_z / l_c)^T \quad (2)$$

In Eq. (1) the quantities u_4, u_5, u_6 correspond to the displacement at the end of a rigid bar of length l_c connected rigidly to the gripped area of the specimen. Reciprocally, the quantities f_4, f_5, f_6 represent the corresponding reaction forces at the end of this rigid bar. This transformation is based on the fact that it maintains invariant the inner product of these two arrays that expresses the total work applied into the system when expressed for every load increment p along the loading path according to

$$W^p = \sum_{i=1}^6 W_i = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^6 \Delta u_i \Delta f_i = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^6 \sum_{a=1}^p (u_i^a - u_i^{a-1})(f_i^a - f_i^{a-1}). \quad (3)$$

In order to establish l_c we consider the possible kinematic constraints of the specimen. Two constraints are identifiable. The first one comes from the fact that we are not interested in taking measurements when, for some loading, the edges of a notch touche each other. This means that the in-plane rotation r_z can never exceed the value that corresponds to the upper edge of the notch touching the lower or vice versa. If the notch and specimen widths are $w_{notch}, w_{specimen}$ respectively, then this implies that the limiting value of r_z is $r_{z0} = 2 \tan^{-1}[(w_{notch} / 2) / (w_{specimen} / 2)]$. The second constrain originates on the estimated maximum norm of any loading path that is programmed into the NRL66.3. If this is defined as length d_{max} , then according to the work equivalence between the [rotation angle, torque] and the [translation, force pairs] pairs as well as from the similar triangles for the case of the specimen in plane rotation we can easily obtain that $l_c = d_{max} / r_{z0} = d_{max} / [2 \tan^{-1}(w_{notch} / w_{specimen})]$.

Loading Space Sampling

The load space is sampled by commanding NRL66.3 to follow radial proportional paths and acquire data at the points that these paths intersect concentric spheres. The term proportional path here means that every path i when represented as a vector starting in the origin and ending at point j , can be resolved to its components in the $(u_1, u_2, u_3, u_4, u_5, u_6)$ frame according to

$$\mathbf{p}_i^j = p_{i1}^j \mathbf{u}_1 + p_{i2}^j \mathbf{u}_2 + p_{i3}^j \mathbf{u}_3 + p_{i4}^j \mathbf{u}_4 + p_{i5}^j \mathbf{u}_5 + p_{i6}^j \mathbf{u}_6 \quad (4)$$

where $p_{i1}^j, p_{i2}^j, p_{i3}^j, p_{i4}^j, p_{i5}^j, p_{i6}^j$ are the magnitudes of each component, and furthermore

$$p_{ik}^j = r_i^j a_{ik}^j, \quad k \in \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6\} \quad \text{with} \quad a_{ik}^j = a_{ik}^{j+1}. \quad (5)$$

We can invoke hyperspherical to Cartesian frame transformation as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} p_{i1}^j &= r_i^j \cos(\varphi_1^j), \quad p_{i2}^j = r_i^j \sin(\varphi_1^j) \cos(\varphi_2^j), \quad p_{i3}^j = r_i^j \sin(\varphi_1^j) \sin(\varphi_2^j) \cos(\varphi_3^j) \\ p_{i4}^j &= r_i^j \sin(\varphi_1^j) \sin(\varphi_2^j) \sin(\varphi_3^j) \cos(\varphi_4^j), \quad p_{i5}^j = r_i^j \sin(\varphi_1^j) \sin(\varphi_2^j) \sin(\varphi_3^j) \sin(\varphi_4^j) \cos(\varphi_5^j) \\ p_{i6}^j &= r_i^j \sin(\varphi_1^j) \sin(\varphi_2^j) \sin(\varphi_3^j) \sin(\varphi_4^j) \sin(\varphi_5^j) \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

In the interest of economy, it is imperative that the least number of specimens is used to characterize a material system. In the past we have used one specimen per loading path with very good results. Since it is meaningless to use one specimen for more than one

path we will maintain this approach. Therefore for each laminate system we will use as many specimens (at least) as the number of paths used to sample the excitation space.

We have established that the number of paths as a function of the dimension n of the space and the number of equatorial points nep is given by [5]

$$n_{paths} = (4 + 4nep)(1 + 2nep)^{n-2} \quad (7)$$

An intermediate scenario could be based on the fact that the rotation components generate motion on the plane they are normal to. Thus, only four out of the six components can be linearly independent. In this case $n = 4$ and for $nep = 1$ Eq. (7) generates 72 paths. This seems to define four 4-d subspaces that can be used for defining the loading paths.

An alternative approach to that of systematically sampling the loading space with regularly distributed loading paths, is that of finding a reduced amount of paths in real time such as the most appropriate information for the model identification process is acquired. To this end, we have recently demonstrated successful application of a hierarchical computational framework with multi-level optimization that demonstrates this [6-8].

Material Geometry Spaces Sampling

The material influences the constitutive response and if our aim is to determine the response of the bulk lamina as opposed to what we test which is a particular laminate, then we need a parameterization that decomposes the lamina from the laminate behavior. For this purpose and in order to maintain low cost we consider obtaining 4 balanced laminate specimen configurations that can be obtained from two balanced laminate plate manufactured productions. By manufacturing balanced laminate plates $[\pm 15]$ and $[\pm 30]$ we can also obtain specimens that can be described as $[\pm 75]$ and $[\pm 60]$ by cutting the specimens out of the original plates in a manner that their y-axis is rotated from the original by 90° . Thus the parameterization of the lamination angle can be expressed by

$$\theta_L \in [15, 30, 60, 75]^\circ \quad (8)$$

In addition, for the case of examining the length scale effects on constitutive behavior one has to address the thickness of the ply, the thickness of the specimen and the specimen dimensions in the x-y plane. Assuming that, as in the case of the lamination angle, we require at least 4 discrete values within the range of the corresponding quantity's parameterization we can now write the formula of the total number of specimens required for a full identification of the material system,

$$n_{spec} = n_{rep} (n_{paths} \times n_{\theta_L} \times n_{LT} \times n_{Lz} \times n_{Ly} \times n_{Lx}) \quad (9)$$

where $n_{\theta_L}, n_{LT}, n_{Lz}, n_{Ly}, n_{Lx}$ are the numbers indicating the cardinality of the ranges where the lamination angle, the lamina thickness, the specimen thickness, the specimen dimension along y-axis and the specimen dimension along the x-axis respectively. The coefficient n_{rep} in front of the right hand side of Eq. (9) is the number of replicates required. A “power” analysis should be used to calculate the number of replicates required. In previous work the coefficient of variation was low so, n_{rep} was set to 2 in an effort to flag outlier data. The overall structure of Eq. (9) clearly indicates that the whole

excitation space is the concatenation of the loading path space (3-6 dimensions) with those of additional 5 dimensions associated with the quantities just described. Therefore, the total excitation space will be 3+5=8 to 6+5=11 dimensional. This is assuming that we have chosen not to parameterize the shape of notches. Since NRL66.3 will be also measuring the 3 to 6- dimensional loading specification at a number of n_{pp} points per path and the corresponding reaction forces for each combination of the excitation space, and n_f particular field quantities (like the components of strain) at n_{op} observation points then the total number of data points acquired for each system will be

$$n_{points} = n_{pp} \times [(n_{spec} + n_{paths}) + n_{spec} \times n_{op} \times n_f] \quad (10)$$

Realistic values in both Eqs. (9) and (10), under the most conservative numerical assumptions, lead to very large values. This underlines the justification for the industrial character of the presented robotic approach.

Strain Space Sampling

A recent addition to our constitutive characterization methodology is the experimental measurement of the strain fields. For this purpose we developed the Mesh Free Random Grid Method (MFRGM) [9-11]. Figure 4 shows an example of typical strain field distributions for a 2-dimensional subspace of the loading space involving tension and shearing of the specimen. The method is being generalized for the 3D case while at the same time is integrated into the computational controls of NRL66.3.

Figure 4. A view of the specimen and the random dot pattern (a), and typical strain distributions ϵ_{xx} (b), ϵ_{yy} (c), and ϵ_{xy} (d).

COMPUTATIONAL PROCEDURE

As described earlier the central theme behind the followed computational approach is that of design optimization where the design variables are the unknown material parameters. The corresponding optimization problem requires the formation of an objective function and associated constraints, such that the solution of this problem will yield the unknown material parameters. The objective function utilized is created from

the balance of mechanical energy of the specimen as a material system. The total work imparted (and measured) into the specimen by the experimental frame (NRL66.3) must balance the volume integral of the total energy density (per unit of volume) spent for deformation and any dissipative mechanisms inside the material according to,

$$\int_V U(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) dV = W, \quad (11)$$

where, U, W are the internal energy density and external work respectively. We assume an additive decomposition of the internal energy density into two parts according to

$$U(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) = \Theta(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) + \Phi(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}). \quad (12)$$

The first part is the usual quadratic elastic energy density,

$$\Theta(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) = \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{C} : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} \quad (13)$$

And the second is the dissipated energy density (DED) spent for any dissipative process into the system. There are many ways one can construct this function. They extend from utilizing a pure interpolation function built from monomials of the strain tensor components, to phenomenological models expressed in terms of the functional evolutions of the elastic strain energy density. Here, as an example, we provide the formulation of a multiplicative decomposition of the DED function according to

$$\Phi(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) = -D(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) \cdot \Theta(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}), \quad (14)$$

where $D(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon})$ is the energetic damage weight of the elastic strain energy density that is to be determined. Introducing Eq. (14) into Eq. (12) yields

$$U(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) = \Theta(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) - D(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) \cdot \Theta(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) = (1 - D(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon})) \cdot \Theta(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}). \quad (15)$$

By postulating that all terms of Eq. (15) are hyperelastic we can recover the general constitutive response by taking the gradient of the result with respect to the strain tensor and applying the chain rule of differentiation as follows

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) = \frac{\partial U(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon})}{\partial \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} = [1 - D(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon})] \frac{\partial \Theta(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon})}{\partial \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} + \Theta(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) \frac{\partial D(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon})}{\partial \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} = \frac{\partial \Theta(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon})}{\partial \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} - D(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) \frac{\partial \Theta(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon})}{\partial \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} + \Theta(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) \frac{\partial D(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon})}{\partial \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}. \quad (16)$$

This relation after Eq. (13) reduces to:

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) = \frac{\partial U(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon})}{\partial \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} = [1 - D(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon})] \mathbf{C} : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} + \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{C} : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} \frac{\partial D(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon})}{\partial \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} = [1 - D(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) + \frac{1}{2} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} \frac{\partial D(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon})}{\partial \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}] \mathbf{C} : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}. \quad (17)$$

By introducing the substitution

$$D'(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) = D(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) + \frac{1}{2} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} \frac{\partial D(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon})}{\partial \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}. \quad (18)$$

And introducing into Eq. (17) we obtain,

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) = [1 - D'(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon})] \mathbf{C} : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}. \quad (19)$$

It is easy to identify that this is the familiar elastic degrading constitutive damage law postulated by various investigators from the continuum damage mechanics community [12-14]. For example, If $D(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon})$ is chosen to be a linear function of the strain tensor of the type $D(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) = \mathbf{a} : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ then Eq. (17) would reduce to (through Eq. (18)) to

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) = [1 - \mathbf{a} : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} + \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{a} : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}] \mathbf{C} : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = \mathbf{C} : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} + \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{a} : \mathbf{C} : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} \quad (20)$$

Where \mathbf{a} would have to be a 2nd order tensor of the linearity coefficients, in order to generate dimensionally consistent results. In this case the energy density will reduce to

$$U(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) = (1 - \mathbf{a} : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) \cdot \Theta(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) = \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{C} : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} - \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{a} : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} \cdot \mathbf{C} : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}. \quad (21)$$

That essentially implies that the DED will be of the form

$$\Phi(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) = -\frac{1}{2} \mathbf{a} : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} \cdot \mathbf{C} : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} \quad (22)$$

We can now form the objective function J based on Eqs. (11), (13) and (22) as follows

$$J = \frac{1}{2} \int_V [\mathbf{C} : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} - \mathbf{a} : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} \cdot \mathbf{C} : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}] dV - W \quad (23)$$

The matrix formulation of Eq. (23) can be derived based on the experimental measurements provided by NRL66.3 data acquisition and control software for the tractions and the pose of the movable grip that determine the externally imparted work W , and the strains on the surface of the specimen via the application of MFRGM. Now the problem of finding the material parameters is reduced to the problem of identifying the elements of the fourth order elastic tensor \mathbf{C} and the second order tensor \mathbf{a} by minimizing the function J subject to the constraint that enforces the positive definiteness requirement for the coefficient expression of the DED according to $\mathbf{a} : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} \geq 0$.

Clearly, this procedure can be generalized for any order polynomial of strain for $D(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon})$ or any rational or irrational function and it can be solved with a plethora of optimization algorithms [15,16].

CONCLUSIONS

We have presented an overview of a framework for the automated composite material characterization. The overall approach was set up as an inverse optimization problem where experimentally acquired data are used to form and determine a material constitutive model. Specifically, descriptions of both the experimental and computational aspects of the framework were presented.

In the experimental procedure description the brief history and description of NRL's 6-DoF mechatronic test loading system (NRL66.3) was given along with the specification of the specimen, loading space, material, and strain field sampling spaces.

In the computational procedure description we presented an internal energy decomposition approach that leads to the formation of an optimization problem with inequality constraints. Solution of this problem leads to the determination of material's linear and non-linear constitutive parameters.

The energetic characterization of composites, is not only useful because it enables the full constitutive modeling of them but also because enables researchers to address the issues of progressive failure in a systematic and application specific manner, by enabling the formation of failure criteria based on energy density concepts.

This is ongoing work and involves multidisciplinary progress on robotic engineering, experimental mechanics and computational modeling.

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